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WILL SABRE-RATTLING ENABLE THE COMPLETION OF THE BANKING UNION?

Abstract: *Due to the decisive stance of the second-term Trump administration, the EU is forced to become capable of defending itself on its own, without relying on the US. This comes at a moment when the threat of global conflicts, primarily with Russia and China, has been heightened, while the technological gap with both of these potential adversaries has been greatly diminished. The European Commission's plan for funding the surge in defense capacities, titled ReArm Europe, which was presented in March 2025, primarily entails increased spending by Member States and mobilization of private sector investments but also the Commission's plan to raise a smaller portion of funds by issuing EU bonds on capital markets. It may be argued that defense is a function which requires a unified system of technological and human resources, which in turn can be financed and maintained only from a genuinely single budget, rather than the one dependent on negotiations and quid-pro-quo arrangements among Member-States. Such budget may only be based on EU-wide mutualization of public debt. Mutualization of debt has already become a stumbling block for the completion of the Banking Union, i.e. for introducing the common backstop in the framework of the European Stability Mechanism, as well as for finalizing the European Deposit Insurance Scheme. The need to tackle the major security threats may unblock these important institutional mechanisms, which would be a major milestone towards creating a genuine EU-level fiscal and taxation union.*

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1. Introduction

The first substantive part of this paper examines the evolving process of unification of the financial systems within the European Union (EU), critically assessing advancements and enduring obstacles in the integration of monetary, banking, and fiscal frameworks. The analysis draws on primary sources, recent policy documents, and academic literature, situating EU financial unification within wider political and economic trends.

The second substantive part of this paper traces the evolution and legal consolidation of the EU's Common Foreign and Security Policy (CFSP), focusing on institutional milestones and recent discourse regarding the formation of a joint EU armed force. The analysis employs primary EU treaty law and academic literature to evaluate the extent and limitations of integration in foreign, security, and defense policy.

The accelerated push for the EU rearmament in response to existential security threats has exposed profound challenges embedded in the Union's unique legal and institutional landscape. As legal frameworks evolve to facilitate an urgent increase in defence capacity, financial institutions (particularly banks) face pressure to overcome reputational, regulatory, and structural barriers to mobilising capital at the required scale. Thus, the third substantive part of this article critically examines the current legal architecture guiding EU defence financing, evaluates the practical role and constraints of banking actors, and offers policy directions for aligning the Union's normative and market realities with its ambitious security agenda.

2. Unification of Finances

European integration has been marked by a progressive deepening of financial and economic union. The adoption of the euro, the creation of a supranational central bank, efforts to integrate banking supervision and regulation, and discussions about fiscal centralization collectively represent ongoing attempts to forge a cohesive framework for economic stability and growth across the EU. However, these processes have encountered both transformative successes and persistent structural deficits (Whelan, 2019: 6). The EU's financial unification is an incomplete process. The monetary dimension has achieved significant integration and stability, but crises underscore the need for stronger banking and fiscal mechanisms. Overcoming political resistance and institutional inertia is key to completing the integration architecture. Deepening financial integration will depend on resolving the remaining impediments, especially those rooted in fiscal centralization and cross-border risk-sharing arrangements.

The integration of financial systems is characterized by three main pillars: 1) the Monetary Union, which focuses on a unified currency and coordinated monetary policy; 2) the Banking Union, established to ensure financial stability and consumer protection across the banking sector; and 3) the evolving framework for a Fiscal Union that seeks to harmonize fiscal policies among member states. The European Central Bank (ECB) plays a pivotal role in these processes, overseeing monetary policy in the Eurozone, while initiatives like the Single Supervisory Mechanism (SSM) and the proposed European Deposit Insurance Scheme (EDIS) aim to enhance banking oversight and crisis management.

2.1. The Monetary Union: Achievements and Limitations

2.1.1. Legal and Economic Foundations

The evolution of financial systems in the EU member states has been significantly shaped by historical events and treaties that aimed at fostering economic integration. The groundwork for this unification was laid with the establishment of the European Monetary System (EMS), which aimed to stabilize exchange rates and foster closer economic ties among member states. This initiative was a precursor to the deeper integration that would be seen in the subsequent decades. The late 1980s and early 1990s marked a critical period for European financial integration. The abolition of capital controls in 1988 initiated a new phase in the integration process, leading to the Maastricht Treaty, which was signed on 7 February 1992 and became effective on 1 November 1993. This Treaty created the European Union and laid the foundations for the Economic and Monetary Union (EMU), thus paving the way for the introduction of the Euro in 1999). The Maastricht Treaty established the criteria for member states wishing to adopt the Euro and reinforced commitment to economic convergence and fiscal discipline among member states.

The transition from the European Monetary System to the Euro was motivated by desires to suppress exchange rate volatility and to capitalize on economic synergies, as articulated in the optimum currency area (OCA) theory. Over time, empirical insights and institutional redesign have shifted the focus from the early OCA theory's limitations toward an understanding of "endogeneity of OCA", the observation that monetary integration can itself foster convergence in the necessary criteria (Mongelli, 2008: 7).

2.1.2. Accomplishments and Problems

The European Central Bank (ECB) has largely achieved its price-stability mandate, maintaining average inflation close to its target (Whelan, 2019:9).

Additionally, the euro is widely supported by citizens in the euro area, which suggests substantial public legitimacy (Whelan, 2019:12). Nonetheless, the global financial crisis and subsequent euro area debt crisis exposed design flaws, including insufficient fiscal coordination and macroeconomic adjustment capacity. The crisis demonstrated the need for more resilient structures beyond mere monetary policy unification, especially as EU Member States confronted asymmetric shocks without recourse to individual monetary or exchange rate tools (Whelan, 2019: 13-14).

2.2. The Banking Union: Integration and Remaining Fragmentation

The Banking Union was launched in response to crises that revealed the risks of fragmented national supervision and resolution frameworks. Its architecture includes: the Single Supervisory Mechanism (SSM), centralizing prudential supervision at the ECB, the Single Resolution Mechanism (SRM) aimed at coordinated bank resolution, and plans for a European Deposit Insurance Scheme (EDIS) whose realization is still pending (Whelan, 2019: 21).

These steps have helped reduce systemic vulnerabilities and created more resilient banks. Yet, true cross-border integration remains incomplete, with banking activities and capital/lending flows still sharply segmented by national lines (European Parliament, 2024: 8).

Despite the centralized supervision, national interests continue to influence key decisions regarding regulation and resolution, hindering deep integration (Beck, Bruno, Carletti, 2024: 2). The absence of a pan-European deposit insurance, and lingering legislative barriers to continent-wide group operations, further contribute to fragmentation (European Parliament, 2024: 23).

2.3. The Fiscal Union: Shallow Centralization, Ongoing Debate

The Fiscal Union remains the least developed pillar of EU financial unification. While some centralization exists via the EU budget and emergency facilities, its size and redistributive capacity are limited (OeNB, 2013:48). The elements such as Stability and Growth Pact, sovereign bailout funds, and fledgling taxation coordination are key but incomplete steps. Proposals for a full fiscal union envision common revenue streams, deeper harmonization of tax and expenditure policies, centralized fiscal capacity, and possibly a euro area treasury (OeNB, 2013:51).

The debate continues over the desirability and feasibility of the fiscal union, balancing potential stabilizing effects against concerns about efficiency,

moral hazard, and national sovereignty (OeNB, 2013: 51). Comparison with federal models elsewhere suggests the EU remains a “shallow” fiscal union—fragmented and limited relative to traditional federations.

3. Development of Common Foreign and Security Policy (CFSP)

The creation of a credible Common Foreign and Security Policy (CFSP) has been a central ambition of European integration, signifying the EU’s desire to act as a global political and security actor. The trajectory from informal cooperation to a structured policy domain marks one of the EU’s most complex institutional evolutions (Smith, 2004: 32).

Legal institutionalization of the CFSP has evolved from informal dialogues to a sophisticated *sui generis* system underpinning the EU’s foreign and security actions. Substantial legal frameworks now exist for defense cooperation but the creation of a joint EU armed force, which is increasingly becoming more plausible, is still subject to legal, political, and operational contingencies that will require further innovation in both EU primary law and practice.

3.1. From the EPC to the CFSP: Foundations and Legal Anchoring

The origins of EU foreign policy cooperation can be traced to the European Political Cooperation (EPC) framework of the 1970s and 1980s, characterized by its loose intergovernmental nature. However, the Treaty on European Union (“Maastricht Treaty”) of 1992 transformed these practices into a legally anchored Common Foreign and Security Policy (CFSP), establishing it as a “second pillar” and incorporating it in the Union’s single institutional framework (Smith, 2004: 36-41). The CFSP legal development accelerated with the Treaty of Amsterdam (1997) and especially the Treaty of Lisbon (2007), which replaced the pillar structure and codified CFSP in Title V of the Treaty on European Union (TEU), outlining an extraordinarily broad scope of CFSP objectives (Wessel, 2016: 444).¹

3.2. Institutional Integration and Legal Characteristics

The EU acquired a regular institutional framework for foreign and security policy with the Lisbon Treaty (2007), by creating the office of the High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy, establishing the European External Action Service (EEAS), and establishing decision-making procedures for adopting binding acts (Butler, 2017: 664).

¹ Wessel, R.A. (2016). Law and Integration in European Foreign and Security Policy, *European Papers*, 1(2), 439-468, https://www.europeanpapers.eu/system/files/pdf_version/EP_ej_2016_2_6_Article_Ramses_Wessel_00052.pdf

Yet, the CFSP remains institutionally distinct: decision-making is driven by the European Council and Council of the EU, usually by unanimity, and excludes the legislative procedures that characterize other policy areas (Wessel, 2016:445). The EU Court of Justice jurisdiction is limited, mostly excluding direct review except for certain procedural or sanctions-related cases (Butler, 2017: 665-666).

3.3. The Road to a Joint EU Armed Force – Policy Innovations: the ESDP and the CSDP

The European Security and Defence Policy (ESDP), later designated as the Common Security and Defence Policy (CSDP), was developed as the operational arm of the Common Foreign and Security Policy (CFSP) to enable the adoption of joint actions in crisis management, stabilization, and peacekeeping (Smith, 2004: 250). The concept of a joint EU military force has recurred in legal and political debates, where the key novelties include the creation of “battle groups” and discussions on Permanent Structured Cooperation (PESCO) (Butler, 2017: 671).

The geopolitical tensions and the Ukraine conflict have reignited proposals for a true European Defence Compact, which could eventually lead to a standing EU force through common financing, harmonized procurement, and joint command (Wolff, Steinbach, Zettelmezer, 2025: 1-2).² Decision-making frameworks such as Permanent Structured Cooperation (PESCO) allow a subset of “willing” Member States to advance integration in defense cooperation (Wolff, et al., 2025: 12-13), as envisaged in Article 42(6) and Protocol 10 TEU. Scholars propose that any standing EU armed force would require a robust treaty basis and significant political consensus (Weinzierl, 2021: 462), while practical and legal hurdles (including national sovereignty concerns) remain formidable (Meijer, Klein, 2025/para.7).³

4. Financing of Europe’s Rearmament: Limits and Prospects

Russia’s renewed aggression in Ukraine and the altered strategic posture of the United States have urged the European Union to exert a historic rearmament effort, aiming to bridge defence capacity gaps and achieve a greater

² Wolff, G.B, Steinbach, A., Zettelmezer, J. (2025) The governance and funding of European rearmament, *Bruegel Policy Brief*, no.15/2025, pp. 1-20; https://www.bruegel.org/sites/default/files/2025-05/PB%2015%202025_0.pdf

³ Meijer, K., Klein, A. (2025). A European Army and Three Difficult Choices, *Verfassungblog*, 5.3.2025; <https://verfassungsblog.de/a-european-army-and-difficult-choices/>.

degree of strategic autonomy in defence procurement and production. However, legal fragmentation, embedded sovereignty clauses, and diverging national interests have complicated the creation of an integrated EU defence market and the effective mobilisation of financial resources. At the centre of this challenge lies the question: can the EU legal and institutional order, in combination with its banking sector, provide a sustainable pathway for collective security and rearmament?

4.1. Legal Frameworks Governing EU Defence Funding

EU competence in defence remains both limited and legally encumbered. Article 346 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) specifically protects member states' prerogatives in defence procurement, justifying exemptions from internal market rules on grounds of "essential interests of security".⁴ While this article permits member states to favour national suppliers, it ultimately sustains market fragmentation and complicates economies of scale in defence production (Beetsma, Buti, Nicoli, 2025: 3). Moreover, the EU's founding treaties do not envision common fiscal instruments for defence procurement, reinforcing a model in which national budgets (rather than supranational mechanisms) constitute the bulk of defence financing (Wolff, et al., 2025: 11). Past efforts to establish a supranational defence entity, such as the failed European Defence Community (EDC) in the 1950s, continue to shape both legal doctrine and political caution (Beetsma, et al, 2025: 5).

4.2. Recent Institutional Innovations

Despite foundational constraints, the traditional paradigm has been changed in the last decade by legislative and institutional innovations. The European Defence Fund (EDF) was established by the Council and the European Parliament in 2019/2020. The Fund started functioning on 1 January 2021, with a total agreed budget of eight billion euros for the period 2021-2027. At the beginning of 2022, the EU enacted a Strategic Compass for Security and Defense, calling for establishment of a new Rapid Deployment Capacity of up to 5,000 troops.⁵ The Act in Support of Ammunition Production (ASAP) was enacted in 2023 in direct response to depletion of ammunition stock among

⁴ Art. 346 of the TFEU. Consolidated Versions of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (2012/C 326/49), 26.10.2012, *OJ of the EU*.

⁵ Council of the European Union (2022). A Strategic Compass for Security and Defence – For a European Union that protects its citizens, values and interests and contributes to international peace and security, Brussels, 21 March 2022, 7371/22 (the Strategic Compass).

Member States due to assistance to Ukraine following the outbreak of the Russo-Ukrainian war.⁶ The European Defence Industry Reinforcement through Common Procurement Act (EDIRPA)⁷ represents a coordinated push towards cross-border defence research, industrial collaboration, and joint procurement (Beetsma, et al, 2025: 11). Although these instruments are still limited in scale, they have delivered modest positive results in joint ammunition and missile procurement, which illustrate the potential of legally supported multilateral arrangements.

A particularly controversial development is the European Commission's use of Article 122 of the TFEU to underpin the SAFE (Security Action for Europe) loan instrument. Originally designed to respond to economic emergencies, Article 122 TFEU has enabled the EU to designate up to €150 billion in loans for defence procurement. This action has been criticized for sidestepping both ordinary legislative scrutiny and national parliaments (Beetsma, et al, 2025: 14). Echoing debates around the SURE and NextGenerationEU facilities, these legal manoeuvres illustrate both flexibility and fragility in the evolving constitutional landscape.

4.3. Procurement Coordination and the Defence Single Market

EU policy has sought to move beyond fragmented national procurement through mechanisms, such as Permanent Structured Cooperation (PESCO), the European Defence Agency (EDA), and expanded mandates for cross-border projects (Beetsma, et al, 2025: 22–23). Yet, these tools remain hampered by opt-outs, the absence of enforceable sanctions, and persistent home-country bias. The European Defence Mechanism (EDM) proposal, which would create a treaty-backed single market among willing states, stands as the most radical vision. It would pool procurement, centralise funding, and introduce clear ownership and usage-fee models for “strategic enablers” such as satellites and major weapons systems (Beetsma, et al, 2025: 27).

4.4. The Role of Banks: Financial Institutions at the Legal Frontline

The mobilisation of capital for EU rearmament critically depends on the engagement of European financial institutions, particularly banks and

⁶ Regulation 2023/1525 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 July 2023 on supporting ammunition production (ASAP) (OJ L 185, 24/07/2023, pp. 7–25.

⁷ Regulation 2023/2418 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 October 2023 on establishing an instrument for the reinforcement of the European defence industry through common procurement (EDIRPA) OJ L, 2023/2418, 26.10.2023.

investment funds. However, EU banks operate within a legal environment shaped by both regulatory and reputational constraints. The regulatory framework is codified in the EU Sustainable Finance Disclosures Regulation (SFDR)⁸ and associated environmental, social and governance (ESG) standards,⁹ which restrict investment in companies associated with “controversial weapons” as defined by international conventions and EU law (Merler, 2025: 2).

Despite these rules, most EU defence companies fall outside the prohibited categories, especially when compared to their global peers. The true impediment arises from self-imposed exclusions by banks and investment funds, motivated by reputational risk, the ESG integration, and public expectations regarding sustainability and armament (Draghi, 2024: 28). By 2021, 14% of managed retail assets in Europe were subject to some restriction on weapons-related investments, a trend unique to the EU and far surpassing the US (Beetsma, et al, 2025: 4).

A pivotal moment occurred in May 2024 when the European Investment Bank (EIB) relaxed eligibility criteria to include primary purpose defence projects, thus ending a long-standing requirement for “dual use with primarily civilian benefit”. This move signaled a substantial and symbolic shift for both public and private sector financiers. As the EU’s signature public bank, EIB’s policy reversal played a cornerstone role in broader capital market attitudes, serving as a benchmark for domestic development banks and commercial institutions alike.

Yet, the EIB’s move has only partially shifted market practice, with private commercial banks continuing to apply tight standards, often encompassing all nuclear weapons and, in some cases, broader defensive technologies, but without clear regulatory guidance from the Commission (Beetsma, et al, 2025:15). The reputational “risk premium” attached to defence investments persists despite softened regulatory interpretation (ESMA, 2024: 5).

⁸ Regulation (EU) 2019/2088 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 November 2019 on sustainability-related disclosures in the financial services sector, OJ L 317, 9.12.2019, 1–16.

⁹ Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2020/1818 of 17 July 2020 supplementing Regulation (EU) 2016/1011 of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards minimum standards for EU Climate Transition Benchmarks and EU Paris-aligned Benchmarks, OJ L 406, 3.12.2020, 17–25.

4.5. Private Capital, Collective Investment Funds, and ESG Dilemmas

The bulk of prospective EU rearmament financing is slated to come not from grants or public loans but from the mobilisation of private capital. The ReArm Europe plan explicitly relies on leverage effects, expecting a €150 billion EU loan portfolio to unlock up to €800 billion in total defence investment through banks and capital markets (EP, 2025: 1).¹⁰ Asset managers, a central channel for transmission of savings into defence industrial investment, remain bound by both regulatory and self-imposed screens.

Banks' lending standards are influenced not only by the ESG (environmental, social and governance) benchmarks but also by concerns over taxonomy-aligned green asset ratios, which could decline sharply if banks increase exposure to non-taxonomy-aligned defence companies. As capital funds envisaged in Article 8 and Article of the EU Sustainable Finance Disclosures Regulation 2019/2088 (SFDR),¹¹ which promote environmental and social objectives (“light green” standard) and sustainable investment objectives (“dark green” standard), continue to apply zero-tolerance or near-zero tolerance to nuclear or weapons-linked revenue, the universe of accessible capital narrows further (ESMA, 2024: 4–6).

4.6. Reconciling Defence and Sustainability Mandates

Redressing the legal and practical barriers to banks' engagement in EU rearmament requires a recalibration of both regulatory and institutional policies. Three key changes are advocated in recent policy literature: (1) Temporarily ease the taxonomy-based restrictions on “controversial weapons”, allowing relevant exposure to count positively in green asset ratios—at least for the duration of the acute security crisis (Merler, 2025: 6); (2) Clarify the legal stance toward nuclear weapons within the EU's sustainable finance taxonomy, affirming that investments in EU-approved nuclear defence projects are consistent with the Union's regulatory framework; (3) Incentivise banks and asset managers (excluding Article 9 funds) to allocate specified proportions of portfolio assets to EU defence sector companies, thus signalling political will and providing a concrete policy “safe harbour” for financial flows (Wolff, et al, 2025: 7).

¹⁰ EU Parliament (2025). ReArm Europe / Readiness 2030 Plan, EU Parliament briefing, EP Research Service, April 2025; [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2025/769566/EPRS_BRI\(2025\)769566_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2025/769566/EPRS_BRI(2025)769566_EN.pdf); See: European Commission/EC (2025). White Paper for European Defence – Readiness 2030, EC, March 2025; https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/e6d5db69-e0ab-4bec-9dc0-3867b4373019_en.

¹¹ Regulation (EU) 2019/2088.

4.7. Overcoming Fragmentation: Towards a European Defence Mechanism

Legal scholarship and policy research increasingly support the creation of a European Defence Mechanism (EDM), a treaty-based institutional vehicle that would centralise procurement and planning for participating members, reduce duplication and outlaw discriminatory state aid or home-country preference. Such mechanism would also serve as a fiscal and legal vehicle for joint borrowing, pooling risks and offering AAA-rated bonds to the market modeled after the European Stability Mechanism (ESM) for euro stability (Wolff, et al, 2025: 1, 16). Finally, from a political perspective, an important aim would be to accommodate non-EU democracies, notably the UK, as full participants, thereby expanding the market and distributing costs.

Such a mechanism would provide binding commitments, pooled financial resources, and a credible legal basis for cross-border banking and investment strategies, thus remedying the chronic tendency for national divergence and under-delivery. The establishment of such mechanism would reinforce de Witte's claim that EU institutional integration has become dependent on joint funding mechanisms (De Witte, 2023: 235).

However, the key weakness of the EU in relation to joint defense thus far has not been either the lack of funding or the lack of technical capacity but the inability to form a joint political will needed for taking on defense-related obligations (Lukić Radović 2024: 237-238).

5. Concluding Remarks

The EU rearmament project is a significant stress test for the Union's legal edifice and the capacity of its banking sector to adapt to new-found security imperatives. Without transformative changes to both regulatory interpretations and institutional design, ambitions for rapid and effective rearmament are likely to be stymied by fragmentation, legal ambiguity, and inertia among private capital providers. Only an approach combining creative legal innovation with proactive banking sector engagement will enable the EU to realise its collective security commitments without sacrificing underlying values of sustainability, rule of law, and market fairness.

It may be argued that defense is a function which requires a unified system of technological and human resources, which in turn can be financed and maintained only from a genuinely single budget, rather than the one dependent on negotiations and tit-for-tat arrangements among Member-States. Such budget may only be based on EU-wide mutualization of debt. Mutualization of debt has already become a stumbling block for the completion of

the Banking Union, i.e. for ensuring the common backstop in the framework of the European Stability Mechanism, and finalizing the European Deposit Insurance Scheme. The need to tackle majority security threats should unblock these important institutional mechanisms, which would be a major milestone towards creating a genuine EU-level fiscal and taxation union. This may happen as a by-product of a new institutional scheme which would mutualize defense-related financial obligations, or as a natural consequence of the expansion of the scope of the already introduced joint debt-issuance schemes.

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ДА ЛИ ЋЕ „ЗВЕЦКАЊЕ ОРУЖЈЕМ“ ОМОГУЋИТИ УПОТПУЊЕЊЕ БАНКАРСКЕ УНИЈЕ?

Резиме

Услед одлучног става администрације САД у другом мандату председника Трампа, ЕУ је присиљена да постане способна да се сама брани, без ослањања на САД. Та потреба долази у време појачане претње од глобалних сукоба, првенствено са Русијом и Кином, при чему је технолошка предност у ова два потенцијална противника битно умањена. План Комисије ЕУ за финансирање наглог повећања одбрамбене могућности, насловљен Поновно наоружавање Европе (ReArm Europe), представљен у марту 2025, првенствено је обухватио повећану потрошњу држава чланица и мобилисање улагања приватног сектора, али је такође обухватио и мањи део средстава која би била прикупљена задуживањем Комисије на тржишту капитала. Може се се тврдити да је одабрана функција која захтева јединствен систем људских и технолошких ресурса, који може бити финансиран и одржаван само из суштински јединственог буџета, који не зависи од преговора и међусобних уступака држава чланица. Такав јединствен буџет може бити заснован само на солидарном прихватању обавеза на нивоу читаве ЕУ, које је већ постало камен спотицања за довршетак банкарске уније, наиме за ступање на снагу уговора о Европском механизму стабилизације, као и за довршетак Европске схеме осигурања депозита. Потреба суочења са великим безбедносним претњама могла би да доведе до деблокирања ових важних институционалних механизма, чиме би био прекорачен важан праг ка стварању суштинске јединствене фискалне и функције опорезивања на нивоу ЕУ.

Кључне речи: банкарска унија, Европска схема осигурања депозита, Европски механизам стабилизације, Поновно наоружавање Европе, фискална унија.

СЕЦИЈА ЗА ТЕОРИЈУ И ИСТОРИЈУ ПРАВА

LEGAL THEORY AND LEGAL HISTORY SESSION

